

Sulphur³⁵: Its Radiochemical Estimation in Sea Water*

D. K. Basu

A method suitable for routine estimation of S³⁵ in sea water is described. The method has been checked, using radiotracers for estimation of 0.005 $\mu\mu\text{c/ml}$ of S³⁵ in sea water.

Deionised primary coolant water used in reactors contains induced radioactivity due to neutron capture reactions. These coolants are bled out periodically in small fractions to keep the corrosion products to a minimum in the circuit.

S³⁵ can be produced either by S³⁴ (n, γ) S³⁵ or by Cl³⁵ (n, p.) S³⁵ reaction. Since the activation cross section for S³⁵ production for natural sulphur is lower (0.011 barn)¹ compared to that of natural chlorine (0.226 barn), more of S³⁵ is formed from natural chlorine.

The periodical bleed out of primary coolant water from the Trombay reactors to the adjoining sea necessitates the analysis of sea water samples to check up the S³⁵ content in it.

In the estimation of S³⁵ in sea water, one meets with difficulties of radiochemically pure recoveries as well as high self-absorption. A method for estimation of S³⁵ in sea water, which can be adopted for routine estimations, is described herein. The method has been checked, using radiotracers, and is sensitive for estimation of 0.005 $\mu\mu\text{c/ml}$ of S³⁵ in sea water.

EXPERIMENTAL

Radiochemical Separation Procedure.—To a 10-ml sample of sea water in a 400-ml beaker were added NH₄OH (0.5 ml) and H₂O₂ (5 ml) and the solution was heated to boiling. ‡ Ethanol (75 ml) and water were added to make the volume 300 ml. Glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and 1M lead acetate solution (5 ml) were slowly added to precipitate PbSO₄ and the mixture was allowed to settle†. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the residue was centrifuged and washed with distilled water. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of saturated ammonium acetate solution (3 to 4 ml will be sufficient), filtered through Whatman 42, and the filter paper was washed with distilled water. 20% Na₂CO₃

* Read at the first Annual Convention of Chemists, held under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society, in Bombay in December 1963.

1. Allen *et al.*, AERE-R 2938, UKAEA-Research Group Report, Radioisotope Data, 1959.

‡ Addition of H₂O₂ and heating are recommended for oxidation as well as for achieving a good exchange between the inactive and active species.

† In presence of ethanol PbSO₄ precipitation will be complete and settling of ppt. will be quicker.

solution (2 ml) was added to the filtrate (or until the precipitation was complete) to precipitate PbCO_3 * and filtered through Whatman 42. The filter paper was washed with distilled water. The excess carbonate was neutralised by adding HCl; the solution was brought to pH 3 and then passed through a Dowex 50 $\times$ 8 resin (50-100 mesh) bed (20 cm $\times$ 1.2 cm) (Am^+ form) at a flow rate of 1 to 2 ml/min $\dagger$. The resin bed was washed with 50 ml of 1M AmAc $\ddagger$.

The solution was diluted and BaSO_4 was precipitated in boiling solution by adding HCl (3-4 ml, conc.) and 1M- BaCl_2 solution (5 ml). After digestion for 5 min. the solution was cooled, allowed to settle, and the residue centrifuged. The residue was washed with 1M-HCl and distilled water. The BaSO_4 precipitate was dissolved in minimum amount of hot ammoniacal 10% EDTA, filtered if necessary through Whatman 42, and reprecipitated** by adding glacial acetic acid (pH 4.5) to the hot solution. The precipitate was digested in a water bath and centrifuged.

The precipitate after washing twice with distilled water, ethanol, and acetone was transferred with acetone to a preweighed brass planchet and evaporated under IR lamp. It was then cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The BaSO_4 source was counted in a β -counter.

Determination of Chemical Yield.—The overall chemical yield* $\dagger$ was determined as follows. From the same amount of sea water (10 ml) BaSO_4 was directly precipitated and weighed in one experiment. With another lot of 10 ml, the entire separation process was completed and the weight of the final BaSO_4 noted. Comparing these two weights of BaSO_4 , the chemical recovery was determined. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	Wt. by direct pptn.	Wt. of BaSO_4 after radio-chemical purification.	% Chemical yield.
1	0.0640 g.	0.0484 g.	75.6
2	0.0654	0.0527	80.6
3	0.0652	0.0515	79.0
4	0.0656	0.0519	79.1
5	0.0647	0.0500	77.3

Calibration

For measurements of β activity of S^{35} , a low-background endwindow G. M. counter was used. In order to determine the absolute disintegration rate, a calibration curve was constructed in the usual way 2 . The standard S^{35} solution used was supplied

* This eliminates most interfering cationic activities including Pb in the insoluble form. Otherwise, Pb will be precipitated with BaSO_4 in the later stage and upset the chemical recovery determination.

$\dagger$ This process removes almost all the cationic contaminations from SO_4^{2-} .

$\ddagger$ To maintain the pH constant.

** This ensures further purification from Sr and other contaminants which form stable soluble complexes under this condition.

* $\dagger$ The radiochemical yield is the same as the chemical yield. This has been confirmed by spiking experiment with S^{35} .

2. Love and Sam, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 336.

by International Atomic Energy Agency with a solid content of 10 $\mu\text{g./ml}$ of Na_2SO_4 and determined with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$. The calibration curve is shown below.

FIG. 1. Calibration curve for S³⁵.

Noting the weight and observed counting rate of the precipitated BaSO_4 in any experiment and referring to the calibration curve, the actual disintegration rate can be determined provided that the sample is counted in the same manner and in the same counter with which the calibration curve has been drawn.

Decontamination Studies.

Decontamination studies were carried out by adding various isotopes of known activities to sea water and noting the activities after complete separation procedure. Table II records the results of decontaminations from various isotopes.

TABLE II

Radionuclides.	Decontamination factor.
Ce ¹⁴⁴ —Pr ¹⁴⁴	10 ⁶
Cs ¹³⁷	107
Sr ⁹⁰ —Y ⁹⁰	107
Zr ⁹⁵ —Nb ⁹⁵	10 ⁶
I ¹³¹	10 ⁶
Mixed fission products (more than 1 year old)	107

In Trombay sea water no detectable S³⁵ activity was found by gas-flow anticoincidence counter. Work was carried out with added S³⁵ activity in sea water. Table III shows results of analysis of added S³⁵ activity in Trombay sea water, obtained after decontamination from fission products.

TABLE III

Sr. No.	S ³⁵ (dpm) introduced in sea water.	Found by this process after necessary correction.
1	9.523×10^4	9.226×10^4
2	9.523×10^3	8.995×10^3
3	1.905×10^2	1.845×10^2

DISCUSSION

The counting of S^{35} in an ordinary G. M. counter is not efficient as S^{35} is a very weak β -emitter (0.167 Mev). For low-active samples, counting can be done either by (a) Windowless anticoincidence G. M. counter or (b) by gas-phase counting as SO_2 or H_2S gas³ or (c) by liquid scintillation counting techniques⁴.

Each of the methods has its own limitations. The best method to obtain simultaneously low background and appreciably high-counting efficiency will be an Umbrella type windowless gas-flow anticoincidence proportional counter, which is under development.

Brass planchets of such thickness have been used as source mounts such that a constant saturation backscattering is obtained. This has an advantage of enhancing the counting rate.

The earlier methods^{5,6} for the radiochemical separation of S^{35} are rather cumbersome and unsatisfactory. A more recent method², where H_2S is released from precipitated $BaSO_4$, is promising, but requires the use of a somewhat complicated apparatus, not very suitable for routine measurements.

Limitation.—In the present method, 10 ml of sea water was taken for S^{35} estimation. This will precipitate nearly 60 mg. of $BaSO_4$. The efficiency of counting in the solid phase will be at least 2%. Taking the counter efficiency as 2% and background 0.1 cpm and assuming a confidence level of 68%, one cannot evaluate S^{35} activity below a level of 0.005 $\mu\mu\text{c/ml}$ even after counting the sample for 1000 minutes, i.e., for more than 16 hrs.

For detecting S^{35} activity lower than 0.01 $\mu\mu\text{c}$, more sea water can be taken and one has to take recourse to a low-background and high-efficiency counting technique. Of course, such low S^{35} activity content has very little practical significance as the MPC value⁷ for S^{35} in water for 168 hr. week is $3 \times 10^3 \mu\mu\text{c/ml}$ for total body.

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3. Merritt *et al.*, *Anal Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 308.

4. Jeffay *et al.*, *ibid.*, p. 306.

5. Metcalf, "Radiochemical Studies", The F.P.—Book I, Coryell and Sugerman, Nation Nuclear Energy Series, Paper No. 47, p. 478, McGraw-Hill, 1951.

6. Reylond *et al.*, ORNL, CF-56-7-118, July 23, 1956.

7. Recommendation of the ICRP., Report of Committee II on Permissible Dose for Internal Radiation, 1959, Pergamon Press.